

CONTINUOUS FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES WITH MULLITE MATRIX DERIVED FROM COLLOIDAL PRECURSORS

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SUMMARY: In this paper, the preparation of carbon and SiC continuous fibre reinforced composites with mullite matrix derived from colloidal-size alumina powder and silica colloids is described. The prepregs was prepared by one infiltration of a fibre tow with high solids yield colloidal sols of 40 vol% containing an oxide composition corresponding stoichiometric mullite, $3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$. The composites were consolidated by hot-pressing at 1550 °C for 0.5 h at 15 MPa to form dense mullite matrix. The microstructures of the unidirectional composites were characterised by XRD and SEM. The structure of the interfaces was examined by TEM. The properties of the composites: flexural strength, modulus and work of fracture were measured by three point bending.

KEYWORDS: SiC, carbon, continuous fibre, colloidal, mullite, matrix, composites, unidirectional, mechanical properties, interface

INTRODUCTION

Continuous fibre reinforced ceramic matrix composites have been extensively investigated for the improvement of the strength and toughness of ceramics, which can be used as structural materials at high temperatures. Densification of the ceramic matrix and control of the interface between fibre and matrix are vital in the production of composites with useful properties [1, 2]. Mullite combines excellent strength and creep resistance at high temperatures with good chemical and thermal stability and a low thermal expansion coefficient of $4.5\text{-}5.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ [3]. Therefore, mullite-containing composites have a potential as a high performance material [4]. In previous work [5-7] it was shown that a sol containing 40% solids by volume, of the mullite composition, $3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$, could be prepared using α -alumina powder and colloidal silica sol. This sol was transformed into a gel from which a mullite monolith was obtained by pressureless sintering at 1600°C for 2 h. A density of $3.10 \times 10^3 \text{ kg / m}^3$ for the bulk sample was obtained, which corresponds to 98% of the theoretical density of $3.17 \times 10^3 \text{ kg / m}^3$ for mullite. The microstructures of the bulk materials have been characterised and the densification mechanism analysed [6, 7]. It was demonstrated that a unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced crystalline mullite matrix composite could be fabricated by one infiltration with this sol and consolidated by hot-pressing [5].

In this paper, the fabrication of composites using colloidal precursors for a mullite matrix is described, in which either high strength carbon or Nicalon silicon carbide fibres were

employed as the reinforcement. The matrix was stoichiometric mullite, $3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$. The microstructures of the composites were characterised by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The fibre-matrix interfacial characteristics were examined by TEM and related to the properties, fracture behaviour and processing conditions of the composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Prepregs of the unidirectional fibre reinforced mullite matrix composite samples were prepared by the single-stage infiltration of the fibre tows with a colloidal sol corresponding to an oxide composition of $3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$, which has been described elsewhere [5], using Ludox colloidal aqueous silica sol (Dupont AS40, 40 wt% of silica particles of 5-50 nm in diameter) and α -alumina powder (Alcoa A1000 SG, with an average size of 0.5 μm) as starting materials. Briefly, the as-received α -alumina powder was dispersed in Ludox colloidal silica sol to produce a homogenous sol. The viscosity of the sol was sufficiently low for the efficient impregnation of the fibre tow. The high solids concentration (alumina-silica mixture) of 40 vol% (68 wt%) enabled single-stage infiltration to be employed for the formation of a dense matrix.

Grafil LXA unsized high strength continuous carbon fibre tow has a diameter of 8 μm , a strength of 4 GPa, an elastic modulus of 224 GPa, a ultimate strain of 1.78% and an average density of $1.81 \times 10^3 \text{ kg / m}^3$. The Nicalon-207 silicon carbide is a polyvinyl alcohol sized continuous fibre yarn which has a strength of 2.6 GPa, an elastic modulus of 189 GPa, a ultimate strain of 1.37%, an average density of $2.55 \times 10^3 \text{ kg / m}^3$ and a diameter of 14 μm . Nicalon-207 SiC polyvinyl alcohol sized fibre yarn was de-sized by passing through hot water at 90 °C, and then stored in vacuum ready for the preparation of the composites.

The composite prepregs were fabricated by infiltrating the continuous fibres using the above sols without additional binder in a single stage. The prepreg was dried in air at room temperature for 48 h and in an oven at 90°C for a further 48 h. By careful control of the solids concentration, composites with a fibre volume fraction in the range of 30-60% could be prepared. In the graphite die assembly, the composite stack of prepregs was sealed by two thick layers of graphite powder to ensure that a reducing atmosphere of CO existed during hot-pressing. The composite samples were consolidated by hot-pressing at 1550°C, for 0.5 h at 15 MPa for the formation of the mullite matrix. All hot-pressed composite samples were allowed to cool naturally to room temperature overnight within the furnace.

The densities of the composite samples, ρ_c were determined by mercury porosimetry using a Micromeritics Pore Size 9320 with a pressure range of ~174 MPa. The volume fraction of fibres in the composites and the crack spacing in the polished surface of the composites were determined by computer-controlled image analysis using an AMS OPTOMAX V. The maximum theoretical density of each composite (assuming no porosity), ρ_{0c} was calculated using the following equation:

$$\rho_{0c} = V_m \rho_m + V_f \rho_f \quad (1)$$

where ρ_m is the theoretical density of matrix; ρ_f is the theoretical density of fibre; V_f is the measured volume fraction of fibre in composite; and V_m is the measured volume fraction of matrix in composite. The phases present in the matrix of the composites were identified by XRD on a Philips 1710 X-ray Diffractometer with the scanning speed of $2^\circ (2\theta)/\text{min}$. SEM was performed on a JEOL JSM6400. TEM was performed on a Philips EM400T. Thin sections for TEM were prepared by ion beam milling a specimen which had been mechanically dimpled to less than $30 \mu\text{m}$ in thickness using fine grinding paste.

The flexural strengths, flexural moduli, and work of the fracture of the composites at room temperature were determined in three point bend on a Mayes Universal Tester at a displacement rate of 0.2 mm/min . The span of the lower support pins was 30 mm , and a span to specimen thickness ratio greater than 20 was employed. Rectangular test specimens cut from hot-pressed cylindrical composite samples were ground and polished to the dimensions of 37 mm in length, 2.0 mm in width and 1.5 mm in thickness. The load-deflection curve for the composites was recorded to fracture. The mechanism of failure was identified by visual examination after the test and by SEM examination of the fracture surface of tested specimens.

The flexural strengths and moduli were determined according to British Standard Methods of Testing (10). The work of fracture was calculated from the area under the load-deflection curve. The ultimate failure strain, ϵ , was calculated by an approximate eqn. (7).

RESULTS

Microstructures of Composites

Figure 1 shows the XRD pattern for the hot-pressed carbon fibre composites hot-pressed at 1550°C , for 0.5 h at 15 MPa . The composite matrix is predominantly crystalline mullite, although a trace of unreacted alumina is evident. For the SiC/M composite hot pressed under the same conditions as the C/M composite, XRD gave a similar result as in Fig. 1. Fig. 2 shows a polished section through the C/M composite approximately parallel to the fibre direction. A dense mullite matrix with a uniform distribution of carbon fibres ($V_f=0.52$) was revealed. No large pores were observed, which was consistent with the measured density of 95% of the calculated theoretical density of $2.46 \times 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$ for the composite. Mechanical polishing resulted in some degree of damage or "pluck-out" at the fibre-matrix interface (white areas indicated by arrows) suggesting that little or no chemical bonding had occurred. Some regularly spaced microcracks were observed in the matrix, which are perpendicular to the fibre direction in fig. 2, which are believed to be induced by thermal mismatch between the fibres and mullite matrix. Thermally induced cracks are produced by stresses resulting from a mismatch in the expansion coefficients of the carbon fibres and the mullite matrix on cooling from the high processing temperature to room temperature. The measured thermal expansion coefficient is $4.83 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for the bulk samples of mullite and that of the carbon fibres is about zero [8]. The thermally induced cracks and the interfacial pores are believed to be the main contributors to the 5% porosity within the C/M composite.

The thermal expansion coefficient for the SiC fibres at $4.0\text{-}5.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ [8] is similar in magnitude to that of mullite. Thus, the potential for thermal mismatch cracking in the SiC/mullite composites is much lower as suggested by the observation of few cracks in a

random polished section through the SiC/M composite (not shown). A polished section perpendicular to the fibre direction (Fig. 3) shows that some fibres were in contact.

Fibre/matrix Interfaces in Composites

The interfaces between the fibre and matrix in the composites were examined by TEM as shown in Fig. 4. A sharply defined interface was observed between the carbon fibre and the mullite matrix in the C/M composite (not shown). Some crevices appear to occur along the interface which would further weaken the interfacial bonding. The crevices are believed to be the consequence of the thermal expansion mismatch between fibre and matrix during cooling. No obvious chemical interaction between fibre and matrix was evident. Some mullite grains near the fibre surface were observed to have grown parallel to the fibre direction. Dislocations were also observed in the mullite grains or along grain boundaries. Evidence for a thin continuous interfacial layer between the SiC fibres and the mullite matrix in the SiC/M composite was revealed by TEM (Fig. 4). Energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) [7] indicated the layer mainly consisted of silica and carbon (amorphous or crystallised). It is possible that the SiC fibre degraded to form a silica layer at high temperatures.

Densification and Mullitisation of Composite Matrices

Highly densified composites were produced including C/M, and SiC/M which have densities ranging from 95 to 98% of the theoretical density (Table 1). Glass viscous sintering is the main matrix densification mechanism as discussed previously (5-7). From XRD and TEM analysis, substantial mullitisation (approximately 90% or more by volume) could be achieved in the matrix. Complete mullitisation was not achieved at 1550 °C for 0.5 h because of the slowness of the interdiffusion processes [9].

During the three point bending test, most of the composites initially showed an elastic response with deflection increasing linearly with increase in load, followed by an extended non-elastic regime. Generally after the maximum value of load was reached, the degree of subsequent extension was strongly dependent on the nature of the interface between fibre and matrix. Figure 5 is representative examples of the stress vs. deflection curves for the carbon fibre mullite composite, C/M and SiC fibre mullite composite, SiC/M, compared with typical results for the matrix materials alone (dotted lines). A summary of hot-pressing parameters together with the properties of the composites is given in Table 1. V_f is the measured fibre volume fraction, ρ_c/ρ_{c0} the ratio of measured to theoretical density expressed as a percentage, σ the ultimate flexural strength, E the flexural modulus, W the work of fracture, and ε the ultimate failure strain. σ_c and E_c are the ultimate tensile strength and the modulus of the composites calculated theoretically according to theory [11]. In the flexural test, employed here, only the outside surface experiences a maximum stress. All failures were initiated on the tensile face of the specimen.

Referring to Table 1, the highest average flexural strength (737 ± 128 MPa) was observed for the carbon fibre reinforced mullite matrix composite hot pressed at 1550 °C for 0.5 h at 15 MPa (C/M). This composite also exhibited the highest work of fracture, 482 ± 122 kJ/m², and ultimate failure strain of $0.37\pm 0.13\%$. These values were considerably higher than those for unreinforced bulk mullite of 150 MPa for σ , 5.18 kJ/m² for work of fracture and 0.001% for ε [11]. Samples of bulk mullite were prepared by pressureless sintering of gels of α -alumina and Ludox silica at 1600 °C for 2 h to 3.1×10^3 kg/m³, approximately 98% of the theoretical

density for mullite, $3.17 \times 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$ [9]. The SiC fibre mullite matrix composite (SiC/M) hot pressed at $1550 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 0.5 h also had a high strength, σ of $630 \pm 98 \text{ MPa}$, W of $293 \pm 111 \text{ kJ/m}^2$, and ϵ of $0.30 \pm 0.1\%$.

Fracture Surfaces Observations

The nature of the fibre/matrix interface can be also revealed by examining the fracture surfaces of composite specimens after the three point test. Extensive fibre pull-out was observed in the fracture surfaces of both carbon fibre and SiC fibre reinforce mullite matrix composites. A typical fracture surface of SEM micrograph from SiC composite is shown in Fig. 6.

DISCUSSION

Strengths and Ultimate Failure Strains

In comparison with the bulk unreinforced matrix materials, all the composites demonstrated an enhanced flexural strength and a change in their fracture behaviour. The flexural strength of these materials correlate directly with the quality of the interfacial bond strength. As expected those materials with a weak interface exhibited tough behaviour (Table 1). However, there is a discrepancy between the experimental values and the theoretical predictions based on the mixture laws (Table 1). The experimental values of strength are lower than the theoretical predictions even assuming that there are no contributions from the matrices. Thus, other parameter needs to be considered. When exposed to high temperatures, carbon fibres oxidise, and the composition and structure of SiC fibres change. Consequently the retained strength of the fibres is affected and also the strength of the composite. Nicalon-SiC fibres generally show reaction even in a reducing atmosphere [12, 13] as follows:

The reduction in strength above $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is caused by microcrystallisation of the fibre structure [12], although the degradation can be alleviated by employing reducing atmospheres [13]. Both a silica phase and the presence of carbon have been detected in the interfacial regions within the SiC/M composite using EDS [7], which are believed to be the products of the above reaction. A severe reduction in the strength of the SiC composites because of the high processing temperatures was also observed, however the longer processing time at $1550 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was not necessary to lead to a reduction in the SiC fibre strength according to the Raman spectroscopy analysis on the SiC fibre composite specimen [14].

Interfaces, Fracture Behaviour and Fibre Pull-out

A glassy silica phase in the interfacial regions between the SiC fibres and matrices of the SiC/M was observed by TEM and defined by EDS. Silica is expected to form on the fibre surface as a product of reaction in equ. 2. A weak interface was observed for the SiC fibre/mullite composite, SiC/M hot-pressed for 0.5 h as shown by the extensive fibre pull-out after the bending test (Fig. 6). In this case the interfacial glass layer between the fibres and matrix in the composite may not be sufficiently thick to form a strong bond.

The influence of the porosity of the composites on the nature of the interface should also be considered. From SEM and TEM observations, some pores and crevices were detected along the interfacial region between the fibres and the mullite matrix within C/M. These pores may have resulted partly from incomplete densification and partly from the volume change during the mullitisation in the matrix, and the crevices may have formed as a result of a relative displacement between fibre and matrix on cooling from high temperature because of thermal expansion mismatch. These pores and crevices could contribute to the weak interfacial bonding, resulting in extensive fibre pull-out on failure (Fig. 5) with a substantial failure strain of $0.37\pm 0.13\%$.

CONCLUSIONS

Carbon fibre and SiC fibre continuous reinforced mullite matrix composites were successfully fabricated by colloidal processing, using α -alumina powder and colloidal silica sol as precursors by one stage infiltration followed by hot-pressing at 1550 °C. Highly densified composites were obtained.

The microstructures of the composites were examined by SEM and TEM. Parallel cracks were observed in the carbon fibre reinforced composites, resulting from thermal expansion mismatch. For the C/M composite a sharply defined interface with little sign of interaction was observed between carbon fibres and mullite matrix, and some crevices were also observed along the interface. A highly densified and nearly crack-free mullite matrix was observed in the SiC/mullite composite, SiC/M. For this composite a thin continuous interfacial silica layer was also observed by TEM and EDS, which may result from reaction at the SiC fibre surface at high temperatures.

Using the three point bending test, the properties of the composites were determined. The highest flexural strength of 737 ± 128 MPa, with the highest work of fracture, 482 ± 122 kJ/m², and ultimate failure strain of $0.37\pm 0.13\%$ were achieved for the C/M. The SiC/M also had a high σ of 630 ± 98 MPa, W of 293 ± 111 kJ/m², ϵ of $0.30\pm 0.1\%$. The fibre reinforcement to mullite is highly effective.

The amount of silica phase along the interface between SiC fibre and matrix is thought to be the main factor controlling the interfacial bonding strength in the SiC fibre composites. The thin silica layer at the interface as shown by TEM and EDS for the SiC/M composite may be account for the relatively weak interfacial bonding observed.

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Table 1: Summary of the hot-pressing conditions and properties of composites

Hot-pressing parameter	1550 °C 0.5 h 15 MPa	1550 °C 0.5 h 15 MPa
Fibre/Matrix	SiC/M	C/M
Number tested	6	6
V_f ($\pm 2\%$)	60	52
ρ_c/ρ_{c0} (%)	98	95
σ (MPa)	630 \pm 98	737 \pm 128
E (GPa)	208 \pm 11	127 \pm 64
W (kJ / m ²)	293 \pm 111	482 \pm 122
σ_c (GPa)	1.6	2.2
E_c (GPa)	149	160

\pm : standard deviation

Figure 1: XRD of mullite matrix carbon fibre reinforced composites of C/M hot-pressed at 1550 °C for 0.5 h at 15 MPa

Figure 2: SEM of polished section parallel to the fibre direction through the C/M composite hot-pressed at 1550 °C for 0.5 h at 15 MPa

Figure 3: SEM of polished cross section perpendicular to the fibre direction through the SiC/M composite hot-pressed at 1550 °C for 0.5 h at 15 MPa

Figure 4: TEM of the interfacial structure between fibre and matrix for the mullite matrix Nicalon-SiC fibre reinforced composite, SiC/M hot-pressed at 1550 °C for 0.5 h at 15 MPa

Figure 5: Typical load vs. deflection plots tested by three-point-bending; behaviour of matrix shown by dotted curves. C/M: Carbon fibre mullite composite C/M, SiC/M: Nicalon-SiC fibre mullite composite

Figure 6: SEM of the fracture surface of SiC/M composite hot pressed at 1550 °C for 0.5 h at 15 MPa, parallel to the fibre direction